

Deep Learning-Based Semantic Segmentation of Thermal Defects Using AResU-Net And Real-ESRGAN for the Infrared Image Resolution Enhancement

Mohammad Siami^{1*}, Tomasz Barszcz², Jacek Wodecki³, Radoslaw Zimroz³

¹AMC Vibro Sp. z o.o., Pilotow 2e, 31-462 Kraków, Poland

²Department of Robotics and Mechatronics, AGH University of Science and Technology, Al. Mickiewicza 30, 30-059 Kraków, Poland

³Department of Mining, Faculty of Geoengeering, Mining and Geology, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, 50-370 Wrocław, Poland

msiami@amcvibro.com*

Abstract. The detection of temperature anomalies in infrared (IR) images is one of the primary challenges of IR imaging methods for condition monitoring and fault diagnosis in industrial infrastructure. The accuracy of the segmentation methods highly depends on the resolution and overall quality of the captured thermal images. Sometimes, high-resolution imagery is not available to cover the desired region of interest in the captured scenes. Furthermore, in robotics-based condition monitoring procedures, the captured thermal images might be blurred due to object motion, camera shaking, and defocusing. In this context, our paper studied the application of an emerging data preprocessing technique called Real-ESRGAN for enhancing the overall resolution of captured IR images by reconstructing lost information. The reconstructed data sets were used to improve the overall performance of the AResU-Net architecture in pixel-level segmentation of thermal defects.

Keywords: Semantic segmentation, Thermal imaging, deep learning, conveyor belt, idler, condition monitoring, REAL-ESRGAN

1 Introduction

The recent advancement in condition monitoring systems has led to an increasing role for mobile robots in performing condition monitoring tasks in harsh environments like deep underground mines. [1]–[5]. Inspection mobile robots might be equipped with different condition monitoring sensors, such as laser doppler vibrometers or high-speed cameras. However, the mentioned equipment are rather expensive or inefficient to be utilized for the CM of large-scale mines.[6]–[11].

The thermal cameras are considered non-contact instruments that can be used for monitoring the thermal states of different machines. [9], [12]–[14]. They are relatively cheaper in comparison to other condition monitoring equipment that can be carried with

inspection mobile robots. As thermal anomalies in bearing surfaces are considered the most common sign of faults in bearings, analyzing the temperature profile of bearings needs to be regularly done to prevent unexpected breakdowns. Different researchers have made contributions to the application of IR imaging methods for the CM of rotating machinery bearings; However, the application of a unified approach for resolution enhancement together with semantic segmentation of thermal anomalies in captured IR images is rarely discussed.[15].

In this research, we proposed a fully integrated approach for automatic upscaling the quality of IR images using a deep learning architecture called Real-ESRGAN for improving the overall performance of the employed CNN network for semantic segmentation of overheated idlers in thermal images.

2 Methodology

In this section, we first focus on the importance of pre-processing stages for improving the overall quality of the extracted frames from captured IR videos. Through the experiments conducted in real-world scenarios, the inspection mobile robot has moved alongside the conveyor belt in an open-case mining site and continuously captured the IR videos from the idlers. Idlers are an important part of conveyor systems that need to be regularly inspected to prevent sudden breakdowns in the production line network.

In order to identify the thermally defective idlers, we first extracted the colored frames and transformed them into gray-scale ones. Moreover, to reduce the size of the original image, we define a constant region of interest in the extracted frames. Through this transformation, we reduce the size of the original frame from 680*680 pixels to 180*180 pixels, which leads to a loss of details over the defined ROI Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Selection of ROI on a captured IR image

To address this issue, we employed a deep learning architecture to increase the resolution of the ROIs. The ESRGAN, or enhanced super-resolution generative adversarial network, is capable of producing high-resolution realistic images without the presence of unwanted noise.[16]. The work of Wang et al. extends the performance of ESRGAN through Real-ESRGAN by training the model with pure synthetic data. [17].

In order to show the performance of the proposed methodology in surpassing unexpected noise we introduced salt and paper noise in original captured frames. For segmentation of overheated idlers in the upscaled IR images, we have trained the AResU-Net with upscaled and originally extracted frames. The AResU-net is developed based on the convolutional neural network (CNN) for performing semantic segmentation tasks.

3 Results and discussion

To analyze the performance of the REAL-ESRGAN model in upscaling the ROIs, we employed no-reference image quality assessment (NR-IQA) metrics. The Blind Image Spatial Quality Evaluator (BRISQUE) is a no-reference image quality score that can be used to measure the overall quality of an image without having access to a reference photo[18]It only uses spatial features (without any frequency-domain features) to measure the image quality. The BRISQUE score is in the range [0, 100]. Lower values of the score reflect the better perceptual quality of the analyzed image. The BRISQUE values in our work range between 0 (Excellent) and 150 (very poor).

Fig. 2. Box plot of REAL-ESRGAN for improving the overall quality of the IR image data set using the BRISQUE score

In Figure 2, we employed the box plot to compare the brisque score of our IR image data set before and after applying pre-processing with REAL-ESRGAN. The resolution and overall quality of original ROIs have been increased using the introduced method from 180*180 pixels into 637*637 pixels. As we can see, we could effectively reduce the mean value of the Brisque score from 38 to 17 while reducing the number of outliers.

After preprocessing our IR image data set, we employed the AResU-Net model with binary cross-entropy as loss function for performing semantic segmentation tasks [19], [20]. To analyze the overall quality of the model, we employed the pixel accuracy and Jaccard index metrics to assess the quality of the segmentation task Figure 4. Moreover, in Figure 4, we analyzed the loss function values through each epoch. To train the model, we used a data set consist of positive cases (overheated idlers) consisting of 817 cases. To improve the overall performance of the employed deep learning network the pre-processed ROIs have been augmented using The combination of different data augmentation techniques, namely: vertical flip, random rotation in 90-degree, horizontal flip and transposes. Finally a data set consist of 4085 frames was used to train the model.

We demonstrate a segmented sample in Figure 3 below together with grey scaled IR image before and after being upscaled by REAL-ESRGAN model.

Fig. 3. IR image changes through the proposed segmentation process

Fig. 4. Comparison of performance factor through the training and validation process

Table 1. Performance comparison of studied methods in segmentation of overheated idlers in IR images

Data set	Semantic segmentation model	Mean accuracy	Mean Jaccard index
Original ROIs with noise	Attention Res U-Net	0.9462	0.8940
Pre-processed ROIs with REAL-ESRGAN	Attention Res U-Net	0.9967	0.9462

From Figure 4 and Table 1, one can notice that improving the overall quality of captured IR images could improve the overall accuracy of the employed deep learning method in correction segmentation of overheated idlers.

4 Conclusion

By employing the REAL-ESRGAN and AResU-Net, we provide a strategy for quickly and accurately diagnosing overheated idlers in IR images. The State-of-the-art deep learning models enable us to drastically improve the overall quality of IR images that, due to the nature of harsh environments, could have low quality. The noise reeducation and image upscaling procedures could enable us to improve the segmentation results. This is significant when assessing critical industrial infrastructures because, due to the nature of the environment, it is rather difficult or impossible to produce high-quality visual information.

Funding

This work was supported by the European Commission via the Marie Skłodowska Curie program through the ETN MOIRA project (GA 955681) — Mohammad Siami. This activity has received funding from the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT), a body of the European Union, under the Horizon 2020, the EU Framework Program for Research and Innovation. This work is supported by EIT RawMaterials GmbH under Framework Partnership Agreement No. 19018 (AMICOS. Autonomous Monitoring and Control System for Mining Plants). Scientific work published within the framework of an international project co-financed from the funds of the program of the Minister of Science and Higher Education titled “ PMW ” 2020–2021; contract no. 5163/KAVA/2020/2021/2.

Acknowledgements

The authors (Mohammad Siami) gratefully acknowledge the European Commission for its support of the Marie Skłodowska Curie program through the ETN MOIRA project (GA 955681)

References

- [1] M. Siami, T. Barszcz, J. Wodecki, and R. Zimroz, "Design of an Infrared Image Processing Pipeline for Robotic Inspection of Conveyor Systems in Opencast Mining Sites," *Energies (Basel)*, vol. 15, no. 18, 2022, doi: 10.3390/en15186771.
- [2] M. Siami, T. Barszcz, J. Wodecki, and R. Zimroz, "Automated Identification of Overheated Belt Conveyor Idlers in Thermal Images with Complex Backgrounds Using Binary Classification with CNN," *Sensors*, vol. 22, no. 24, 2022, doi: 10.3390/s222410004.
- [3] Ł. Bołoz and W. Biały, "Automation and robotization of underground mining in Poland," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 20, p. 7221, 2020.
- [4] I. D. Miller *et al.*, "Mine Tunnel Exploration Using Multiple Quadrupedal Robots," *IEEE Robot Autom Lett*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 2840–2847, 2020, doi: 10.1109/LRA.2020.2972872.
- [5] A. Li, D. Ye, E. Lyu, S. Song, M. Q. H. Meng, and C. W. De Silva, "RGB-Thermal fusion network for leakage detection of crude oil transmission pipes," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Biomimetics, ROBIO 2019*, 2019, pp. 883–888. doi: 10.1109/ROBIO49542.2019.8961733.
- [6] M. Siami, T. Barszcz, R. Zimroz, and J. Wodecki, "Robot-based Damage Assessment Method for Identification of Overheated Idlers in Conveyor Systems Using Histogram Analysis Techniques," May 2022.
- [7] M. Siami, H. Shiri, T. Barszcz, and R. Zimroz, "Unsupervised Learning Based Data-Driven Anomaly Detection for Acoustic Monitoring of Idlers in Conveyor Systems," May 2022.
- [8] M. Siami, P. Trybała, T. Barszcz, and R. Zimroz, "A Sensor Fusion System with Thermal Infrared Camera and Lidar for Automatic Detection and Localization of Overheated Idlers on Conveyor Systems," May 2022.
- [9] S. Vidas, P. Moghadam, and M. Bosse, "3D thermal mapping of building interiors using an RGB-D and thermal camera," in *Proceedings - IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*, Sep. 2013, pp. 2311–2318. doi: 10.1109/ICRA.2013.6630890.
- [10] J. Du, K. Chen, Q. Liu, and J. Wang, "Application of Infrared Thermal Imaging Technology in Fault Diagnosis of Mine Car Wheels," in *2019 IEEE 3rd Information Technology, Networking, Electronic and Automation Control Conference (ITNEC)*, 2019, pp. 1288–1291. doi: 10.1109/ITNEC.2019.8729413.

- [11] M. Siami, H. Shiri, T. Barszcz, J. Wodecki, and R. Zimroz, "Information Fusion of Infrared Images and Acoustic Signals for Bearing Fault Diagnosis of Rotating Machinery," in *Surveillance, Vibrations, Shock and Noise*, 2023.
- [12] A. Procházka, H. Charvátová, O. Vyšata, J. Kopal, and J. Chambers, "Breathing analysis using thermal and depth imaging camera video records," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 17, no. 6, p. 1408, 2017, doi: 10.3390/s17061408.
- [13] T. Dutta, J. Sil, and P. Chottopadhyay, "Condition monitoring of electrical equipment using thermal image processing," in *2016 IEEE First International Conference on Control, Measurement and Instrumentation (CMI)*, 2016, pp. 311–315. doi: 10.1109/CMI.2016.7413761.
- [14] L. E. Montanez, L. M. Valentin-Coronado, D. Moctezuma, and G. Flores, "Photovoltaic module segmentation and thermal analysis tool from thermal images," in *2020 IEEE International Autumn Meeting on Power, Electronics and Computing (ROPEC)*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [15] T. Barszcz, M. Siami, J. Wodecki, and R. Zimroz, "Automated IR Image Segmentation for Identification of Overheated Idlers in Belt Conveyor Systems Based on Outlier-Detection Method," *SSRN Electronic Journal*, May 2022, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.4054247.
- [16] X. Wang *et al.*, "Esrgan: Enhanced super-resolution generative adversarial networks," in *Proceedings of the European conference on computer vision (ECCV) workshops*, 2018, p. 0.
- [17] X. Wang, L. Xie, C. Dong, and Y. Shan, "Real-esrgan: Training real-world blind super-resolution with pure synthetic data," in *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*, 2021, pp. 1905–1914.
- [18] A. Mittal, A. K. Moorthy, and A. C. Bovik, "No-reference image quality assessment in the spatial domain," *IEEE Transactions on image processing*, vol. 21, no. 12, pp. 4695–4708, 2012.
- [19] N. Mu, Z. Lyu, M. Rezaeitalshmahalleh, J. Tang, and J. Jiang, "An attention residual u-net with differential preprocessing and geometric postprocessing: Learning how to segment vasculature including intracranial aneurysms," *Med Image Anal.*, vol. 84, p. 102697, 2023, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.media.2022.102697>.
- [20] C. Li, M. Chen, J. Zhang, and H. Liu, "Cardiac MRI segmentation with focal loss constrained deep residual networks," *Phys Med Biol.*, vol. 66, no. 13, p. 135012, 2021.